

Deviant Behavior in Individuals and Impact in Society

Inconsistent behavior in humans is often labeled as distinct behavior which occurs in the humans, when they fail to achieve the socially approved goals by the legitimate means. Various structural factors resulting in the biasness of the society is responsible for the development of deviant characters in human beings.

Biasness and prejudices deeply affect the cognitive state of mind due to which the deviant behavior further goes on at an increasing rate. Similarly excessive strain and pressure, too leads to deviant characters. On speaking shamelessly, about the cultural state of our society, the members of our society have established a set of doctrines to achieve successful goals by using the legitimate means provided to them.

On the other hand, the same set of structural factors and cultural factors are responsible for creating fragments, in the society, on the basis of caste, creed, race or genders, which leads the feeling of discrimination among the individuals, giving rise to the pressure and strain. Deviant behavior helps to generate quick responses, to the strain encountered by the humans. As a result, the individuals develop the habit of conformity, in which they accept the culturally approved doctrine, and goals, and begin paving them road to achieve them legitimately.

Similarly, deviant behavior increases the innovation in the humans, which makes them more creative but if taken, in an opposed fancy can give rise to the habit in an opposed fancy, can give rise to the habit in the individuals of achieving them by other illegitimate means. With the sands of time, individuals, either adopts ritualism, by carrying on the rules for their own sake, or adopts retreatism by rejecting all values and norms of society, and opts to stay out of the society.

Failure in both of the above means leads to the development of rebellion feelings, as the individuals, replaces existing goals and attempts to establish a new set of social doctrines bringing a drastic change in the society. Since the same social structure can give rise to both normal and deviant behavior. It helps us to analyze the crime rates in the society. Statistically it has been found out that peoples among the working class have higher crime rates, as they have limited, opportunity for earning in an accordance with low. Our contemporary society bears the seeds of uncertainty between the biological impulses of the humans and the social structure set by the established social doctrines.

Conformity leads to the state of unaided reasoning, so in order to make our society more social, we must be able to establish society free of biasness and prejudices. If we are able to stop the deviant behavior arising in the different individuals of our society then only we can make our society more better.